

SAME YARDSTICK, DIFFERENT RESULTS: EFFICACY OF RUBRICS IN SCIENCE EDUCATION ASSESSMENT

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Abstract

Assessments have become integral to today's teaching and learning. Within the world of assessments, there are two paramount ideologies at work: assessments for learning and assessments of learning. The latter are typically administered at the end of a unit or grading period and evaluate a student's understanding by comparing their achievement against a class, nationwide benchmark, or standard. The former assesses a student's understanding of a skill or lesson during the learning and teaching process. Assessment for learning enables teachers to collect data that will help them adjust their teaching strategies, and students to adjust their learning strategies. In order to achieve this goal, teachers can make use of several assessment tools, such as concept maps, oral presentations, peer review, portfolios, examinations, written reports, and rubrics. The use of rubrics not only makes the teacher's standards and result grading explicit but can give students a clear sense of what the expectations are for a high level of performance on a given science assignment. In this study, quantitative data were collected from tasks, assessed by 10 teachers who were purposefully sampled; while qualitative data were collected from interview responses of the same teachers to explore the extent of uniformity in the use of rubrics. The researchers compared and analyzed the different scores, allocated by the respective participants, and analyzed the qualitative data using qualitative data analysis. The study suggests that if interpreted and used well, rubrics support learning by enabling an efficient, consistent, objective, and quick way of assessing students' work thereby facilitating learning.

Keywords: assessment of learning, rubrics, science education, assessment for learning.

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1. Introduction

The end goal of assessment is to gather relevant data about student performance or progress in a particular learning area, or simply to establish student interests to make inferences about their learning processes [1]. With this information at hand, respective teachers can reflect on each student's level of achievement, as well as on specific inclinations of the group, to customize their teaching plans [2]. Good and appropriate assessment encourages the understanding of teaching as a formative process that evolves over time with feedback and input from both teachers and students [3, 4]. Six types of assessment of learning are diagnostic, formative, summative, norm-referenced, criterion-referenced, and interim or benchmark [5, 6].

All of the different assessment types work together to provide a completely valid, reliable, and fair picture of a student's learning journey [7]. In order to achieve this goal, teachers can make use of several assessment tools, such as concept maps, oral presentations, peer review, portfolios, examinations, written reports, and rubrics [8, 9]. Assessment can reinforce the efficacy of teaching and learning and forms a core part of the South African high school Physical sciences curriculum. Physical Sciences comprises two subjects, namely Physics and Chemistry. The purpose of Physical Sciences is to make students aware of their environment and to equip them with investigating skills, relating to physical and chemical phenomena, for example, lightning and solubility [10]. Examples of some of the skills that are relevant for the study of Physical Sciences are classifying, communicating, measuring, designing an investigation, drawing and evaluating conclusions, for-

ulating models, hypothesizing, identifying and controlling variables, inferring, observing and comparing, interpreting, predicting, problem-solving and reflective skills [11].

In this learning area, twelfth-grade students are assessed through informal assessment tasks, such as homework, classwork, practical investigations, experiments, and informal tests [12]. These students are also assessed through formal assessment tasks, such as control tests, examinations, projects, and practical investigations [13]. According to the South African education system, control tests and examinations are assessed using memoranda, whereas rubrics are used for projects and practical investigations.

1. 1. Use of rubrics in student assessment

An assessment rubric is a written criterion that details expectations of what students will need to know and be able to do in order to receive a given grade [14] and these help teachers to develop clear learning objectives for their students. It divides the assigned work into component parts, providing clear descriptions of the characteristics of the work, associated with each component, at varying levels of mastery [7]. If rubrics are provided to students prior to the assessment activity, they serve to guide students' efforts and focus. Rubrics are meant to support learning by enabling an efficient, consistent, objective, and quick way of assessing students' work. By developing a working guide (rubric) for students to use as a tool throughout the assignment [5], Physical Sciences teachers provide the scaffolding necessary to improve the quality of their students' work and to increase the scientific knowledge that the students acquire.

Properly designed and interpreted rubrics allow the teachers to accommodate and differentiate for heterogeneous classes by offering a range of quality levels [7]. Rubrics can be used with gifted, average, and academically challenged (learning support) students. Rubrics provide students with a clear understanding of what is expected of them and gives them (students) concrete directions about what makes a good science practical investigation [3, 8], thus making the grading process more transparent. The idea of the rubric in the science classroom is to encourage accountability, while making grading consistent and meaningful to both the student and the teacher [15].

A body of research has proven that rubrics improve students' end products and thus increase the students' overall learning in science [2, 6, 7, 8,]. In a study on the efficacy of rubrics as assessment tools, [14] equally assigned two hundred and eighteen third-year pre-service students to either the control or experimental group. The experimental group was allowed to use rubric self-assessment for designing a conceptual map. The results showed that the rubric group reported higher learning strategies use, performance and accuracy.

In another study, [16] analyzed the effects of rubrics and self-assessment scripts on self-regulation, learning, self-efficacy and goal activation using 85 university students, enrolled in a psychology course on Motivation and Emotion. During the study, the participants summarized texts and designed conceptual maps of each topic unit with the help of rubrics. The results of the study showed that the use of rubrics increased the participants' learning. [17] investigated the effects of having 5th, 6th, and 7th graders read a model written assignment, generate their own list of criteria, and use rubrics to self-assess the quality of the written stories and essays they then produced. A comparison group brainstormed criteria and self-assessed their drafts but did not use the rubric. Controlling for previous writing ability, the group that used the rubrics for self-assessment wrote better overall, and specifically in the areas of ideas, organization, voice, and word choice [7].

[18] reviewed the findings of studies of the use of rubrics in education settings, published from 2005 to 2013. The review included studies only if the rubrics involved met the definition of having coherent sets of criteria and performance level descriptions for those criteria. Their review suggests that rubrics yield information of sufficient quality if certain conditions are met, most notably having clear and focused criteria [10]. Evidence regarding the effects of rubrics on performance is positive overall with positive associations between rubric use and motivation to learn, being identified in some studies.

Clearly written and well-designed rubrics, not only can they be used to formulate standards for levels of academic accomplishment and used to guide and improve performance in Physical Sciences but can also be used to make these standards clear and explicit to students [19]. Although

the use of rubrics is common practice in the twelfth-grade Physical Sciences setting, it is imperative to know how many teachers and students can adequately interpret and use them effectively to facilitate learning. The claim that rubrics can promote learning and achievement has intuitive appeal but there is only limited empirical evidence to support it [15, 17], especially in the context of South African science classes. The present study sought to establish the efficacy of rubrics in assessing practical activities in a twelfth-grade Physical Sciences class in South Africa.

2. Materials and Methods

The current study made use of a mixed-methods approach. According to the [11], practical investigations must be integrated with theory to strengthen the concepts being taught and may take the form of simple practical investigation or even an experiment. In the twelfth-grade, South African Physical Sciences students are expected to conduct at least seven practical investigations. Three of these practical activities are prescribed and done as part of the formal assessment with the rest being done as part of the informal assessment [20]. Formally- assessed practical investigations contribute 25 % towards a twelfth-grade Physical Sciences student's final mark [11]. In assessing these practical activities, whether done for formal or informal assessment, Physical Sciences teachers use rubrics to evaluate their students' work.

2. 1. Research Question

The present study sought to investigate the efficacy of rubrics in assessing twelfth-grade science practical activities. The research question was: How effective are rubrics in assessing practical activities for twelfth-grade Physical Sciences students?

2. 2. Participants and Site

The current study, carried out in the year 2019, aimed to investigate science teachers' perceptions and practices towards the use of rubrics in assessing science practical activities. The research participants were 10 newly-qualified, permanently employed teachers in 10 secondary schools in Soweto, South Africa. Soweto is a culturally-hybrid township, home to over 1.5 million people from various countries [21]. The township is in Gauteng province and borders Johannesburg's mining belt in the south. Its name is an English syllabic abbreviation for South Western Townships and was created in the 1930s when the then White government started separating blacks from whites, creating black townships [22].

Purposeful sampling, also known as purposive and selective sampling, was used to identify the participants as they were best suited to provide in-depth and detailed information about the phenomenon under investigation in Soweto secondary schools. The 10 participants in the present study are Physical sciences teachers who obtained their teaching qualifications from four different South African universities in the year 2018. They all hold a four-year Bachelor of Education degree, specializing in the teaching of Physical sciences at Further Education and Training (FET) phase. The FET phase ranges from the tenth to the twelfth grade and these FET phase teachers, according to the South African education system, teach one or more subjects within a prescribed curriculum per grade, and promote the students' social, emotional, intellectual, and physical development [11]. All participants in the present study teach Physics and Chemistry to twelfth-grade students and use rubrics in assessing students' practical activity write-ups.

2. 3. Data collection

During the study, the 10 participants were given an exemplar practical activity write-up, extracted from the [20] Physical Sciences School-Based Assessment Exemplars CAPS Grade 12-learner guide. The task was based on a topic from the Physics component, *Mechanics*, a topic the participants had taught and assessed their twelfth-grade students. According to the Physical Sciences curriculum, at the end of the teaching session, students are expected to carry out a practical activity, in which they determine the velocity and acceleration of a number of objects of their choice. The students will then come up with a write-up, detailing every step they followed

during the practical activity, their conclusions, and recommendations, and submit the write-up to the teacher for assessment. The teachers will then assess the write-up using a rubric.

In order for the participants to assess the given task in this study, they were given the same rubric and asked to assess the same write-up. The activity was marked out of 20 and converted to a percentage. As a pilot study, the same task and rubric had been given to two science education senior lecturers, Dr. X and Prof Y, from 2 different universities in the country. The two senior lecturers assessed the task independently and in confidentiality. After the participants had scored the practical activity and the researcher had analyzed the scores, the researcher then held a focus group interview with the participants. The interview session lasted about sixty minutes and was held in the English language. The interview responses were written and tape-recorded concurrently by the researcher with the participants' consent, ensuring data was captured accurately for analytical purposes.

In reporting the findings from the study, triangulation of data, thick descriptions, and quotes from the participants are intended to ensure the validity and trustworthiness of the research [23]. During the study, the participants chose their own pseudonyms for anonymity and confidentiality purposes.

2. 4. Data analysis

Quantitative data were analyzed using descriptive statistics [23]. The researcher compared and analyzed the different scores, allocated by the respective participants. The interview data were analyzed using qualitative data analysis, an approach, grounded in [24]'s model. The analysis model produces an information base that is structured by categories and can be used in the subsequent search for patterns in the data and integration of these patterns into a systematic, theoretically embedded explanation [24, 25]. The research did not have any a priori themes.

3. Results

Whether used with students to set learning goals, as scoring devices for grading purposes, to give formative feedback to students about their progress toward important course outcomes or for assessment of curricular and course innovations, rubrics allow for both quantitative and qualitative analysis of student performance in science education [3]. The qualitative analysis could yield narrative accounts of where students, in general, fell in the cells of the rubric, and they can provide interpretations, conclusions, and recommendations, related to student learning and development, aspects that can be helpful to the teacher.

3. 1. Quantitative data

Results from the study show that 5 out of the 10 participants assessed the task, given to them, and concluded that it was below the Department of Basic Education's expected standard. According to the [11], a student should attain 30 % or higher to obtain a pass in Physical sciences. The 5 teachers, therefore, awarded the task scores below 30 %, with the lowest score being 10 %. Meganne and Oley, two of the participants scored the task at 55 % and 70 % respectively. Puleng gave the practical activity a 70 % mark, Tumelo gave it an 80 %, and the highest score came from Jabu who evaluated the task and awarded it 85 %. The two senior lecturers, Dr. X and Prof Y, scored the task at 60 and 65 % respectively. Considering these scores, it is evident the participants interpreted the rubric differently, with one participant awarding a score of 10 % and another awarding 85 % for the same assessment task.

3. 2. Qualitative data

After having analyzed the scores, awarded by the different teachers, and noted the difference in the marks, the researcher then went on to interview the 10 participants to determine the possible causes of the difference in the scores they had awarded the task, and also to get their perceptions of the use of rubrics in assessing practical activities in Physical sciences.

Presented and discussed below are interview responses from the 10 participants:

3. 2. 1. *What are your experiences in using rubrics to assess students' practical work?*

Seven of the ten participants highlighted that they had problems in using rubrics when assessing students' work. Lerato, one of the participants who had awarded the task a failing mark, said:

At university, we were not taught how to use rubrics when assessing students even though lecturers used them to assess us.

Her concerns were similar to those of Palesa, who said:

In our assessment course at the university, we were taught the advantages and disadvantages of using rubrics but not how to use them. This is something our lecturers assumed.

Considering the two responses, some universities assume pre-service teachers are in a position to effectively use rubrics for assessment purposes. This assumption is also held by the prospective employer, the South African Department of Basic Education (SA DoBE), according to Shepherd who said:

I agree with what Palesa has just said. Even the SA DoBE, principals, and heads of department do not orient us on how to use rubrics. Everyone assumes that since we are qualified teachers, we know everything.

These responses suggest the existence of a gap between theory and practice. While some universities shortchange students in this regard, schools, on the other hand, assume they are employing people who are assessment literate and are in a position to use the various assessment tools at their disposal. With the later in mind, schools, according to the interview responses, leave everything to do with assessment in the hands of the respective learning area teachers. However, according to Kamogelo, there is yet another problem, associated with the rubrics they are given by the SA DoBE:

The language, used in some of those rubrics, is difficult to understand. In the end, I just read the student's work and give a mark I think is best without using the rubric. I fail to see the alignment between the expectations and the marks allocated.

This response suggests that rubrics are not entirely self-explanatory. Both the assessor and the assessed need help in understanding rubrics and their use. One way to go about it would be for all concerned parties to co-create the rubric. This might make everyone aware of the expectations and enables relatively fair use of the assessment tool. The SA DoBE or head of the science department at the respective school can also co-create the rubric with the teachers, explaining the contents of the rubric and how best to use it. The teachers, in turn, could also do the same with their students. In both cases, the participants need to be given a bit of practice by doing a mock critique. In developing rubrics, the present study also suggests that simple, precise language should be used. This eliminates the chances of misinterpretations by the users.

3. 2. 2. *Do you think using rubrics for assessment enhances students' learning of science?*

A rubric, because it forces you to break down specific attributes and changes you want to assess, directs your attention on different bits and pieces of a project [7]. If rubrics are to facilitate learning in Physical Sciences, then issues of validity, reliability, and fairness have to apply to rubrics, too. There is a need for teachers to worry more about the quality of the rubrics that they use. One suggestion, emanating from the present study, is that a rubric must be aligned with reasonable and respectable standards and with the curriculum, being taught in order to be valid. To facilitate effective learning, the rubric must pass a test of reliability by resulting in similar ratings when used by different people.

In the present study, the same rubric resulted in ten different marks, being awarded for the same activity, ranging between 10 % and 85 %. In explaining the vast difference in marks, Roxanna said:

Those rubrics, given to us, are too prescriptive. They don't leave room for diversion and at times it is difficult to use them. I can't even give my students feedback based on the rubric. As a result, I give them the feedback I think is best.

Contributing to the same question, Ray added:

A rubric is a fair assessing tool. They are objective. However, to enhance academic performance in science, students should be given these before they embark on the assessment task. The

present case is that students are given rubrics as attachments to their assessed work. We need to explain the assessment criteria to the students beforehand.

If used properly, rubrics are an easily applicable tool for supporting learning, assessment, and evaluation in the science classroom. They offer a process for defining and describing the important components of complex tasks and behaviors. The teacher can use them to clarify the learning goals, design instruction that addresses those goals, communicate the goals to students, guide feedback on students' progress toward the goals, and judge final products in terms of the degree, to which the goals were met [7]. For effective use, the present study suggests the use of rubrics before, during, and after lesson delivery. This is in line with Nompilo's contribution who said:

Rubrics help my students understand the goal of the activity and focus their efforts. I often create a rubric with my students by discussing strong and weak examples of students' work with them and during that process we iron out any misunderstandings. That way, the use of a rubric will definitely enhance my students' learning.

Puleng had a different view of this:

Rubrics can only enhance students' learning if they are in the right hands. In my case, I hardly know how to use them and as such, I cannot claim that my students are benefitting from their use. The teacher has to know and understand how to use them first before expecting students to benefit. If I can be able to use them, then I will be in a position to give valuable feedback to my students.

Research has shown that feedback can improve learning, especially when it gives students specific information about the strengths and weaknesses of their work [2]. The problem is that this can only happen, according to Puleng, if the teacher understands the rubric and can use it effectively. When this happens, the teacher will be in a position to provide individualized, constructive critique in a manageable timeframe [7, 26], resulting in enhanced learning. By simply marking appropriate boxes on a rubric and give it back with an assignment, the teacher would still have provided more feedback about the strengths and weaknesses of the work than just assigning a mark or letter grade [14]. The teacher can, in addition to a marked up rubric, give their students written and verbal feedback.

3. 2. 3. In assessing the science task, given to you, how did you arrive at the final score?

With regard to this question, different responses came from the participants. Thelma, the participant who had awarded the task the highest score (85 %) said:

I used the rubric. As I went through the task I constantly referred to the rubric in awarding marks. I, however, awarded extra marks for clarity and coherence, something that wasn't covered by the rubric.

Adding to the conversation, Shepherd said:

I read through the whole activity first before grading it. Since I am not yet good at using rubrics, I looked at the layout, presentation, and use of appropriate language. That's how I came up with a mark of 20 %.

In agreement with this were two other participants, Palesa and Mmabatho. Although the rubric has emerged as one of the most popular assessment tools in progressive educational programs, there is an unfortunate dearth of information in the literature, quantifying the actual effectiveness of the rubric as an assessment tool when being used by newly qualified teachers. Results from the present study suggest that rubrics can only be effective if the teachers are well-versed in using them. A good rubric can enhance the academic learning of Physical Sciences students if both the teacher and student are fully aware of the expectations and can interpret the rubric well.

In a study by [27], the three investigated college biology students' use of rubrics for peer assessment and teacher assessment of a collaborative oral presentation. The rubric looked at five criteria, namely, organization and research, persuasiveness and logic of the argument, collaboration, delivery and grammar, and creativity and originality [16]. Originally, the rubric was developed by the course lecturers and then modified with discussion and involvement of all students. For their study, the researchers used the same rubric for a required course assignment three years in a row. The course lecturers were interested in finding out whether the information students gained from peer evaluation was accurate, matched lecturer input, and whether this accuracy was consistent

across different years and classes. The short answer was yes. Students were able to accurately give feedback to their peers, their information matched that of their instructor, and this was the case for each class [16, 17, 28].

4. Discussion

When used as teaching tools, rubrics not only make the teacher's standards and resulting grading explicit, but they can give students a clear sense of what the expectations are for a high level of performance on a given science assignment, and how they can be met. This use of rubrics can be most important in enhancing learning in the science classroom. Although the time, expended in developing a rubric, can be considerable [13], once rubrics are in place they can streamline the grading process and affords the teacher ample opportunity to give feedback to the students on different components of the assignment [6]. Once the science teacher has created a rubric, the same rubric can be used for a variety of activities. Reviewing, reconceptualizing, and revisiting the same concepts from different angles can improve the understanding of concepts for students [5].

The more specific the rubric, the less the requirement for spontaneous written feedback for each piece of student work. Although provided with fewer written comments that are individualized for their work, students nevertheless receive informative feedback [10]. When information from rubrics is analyzed, a detailed record of students' progress toward meeting desired outcomes can be monitored by the teacher, and then provided to students, so that they may also chart their own progress and improvement [8]. If properly used, rubrics encourage reflective practice on the part of both students and teachers. In particular, the act of developing a rubric, whether or not it is subsequently used, instigates a powerful consideration of one's values and expectations for student learning, and the extent, to which these expectations are reflected in the actual science classroom practices [7].

If rubrics are used in the context of students' peer review of their own work or that of others [10], or if students are involved in the process of developing the rubric [13], these processes can spur the development of their ability to become self-directed and help them develop insight into how they and others learn [6]. Rubrics also enable the teacher to match their observations of a student's work to the descriptions in the rubric, hence averting the rush to judgment that can occur in classroom evaluation situations. Rubrics also facilitate learning because, instead of judging the performance [13], the rubric describes the performance [14]. When rubrics are used, the resulting judgment of quality also contains within it a description of performance that can be used for feedback and teaching purposes. This is different from a judgment of quality from a score or a grade, arrived at without a rubric [3, 13]. Academic performance judgments without descriptions stop the action in a classroom, something which rubrics guard against.

As seen in the present study, although the same criteria are considered when using the same rubric, interpretations, and grading can vary according to one's level of expertise. In line with Ray (one of the participants)'s observation, a rubric is a working guide and should be handed to the students before the assignment begins in order to get students to think about the criteria, on which their science work will be assessed. The premise of rubrics is that assessment and learning are inseparable [7].

Rubrics then are the springboard for learning: The starting place for all effective instruction is designing and communicating clear learning goals [29]. Although using rubrics allows students to know exactly what is expected of them, this can only happen if the teachers can interpret the rubrics themselves. Rubrics can be used for daily assignments, projects or even exams [8]. A rubric has specific guidelines for what is expected from a scientific activity and gives quantitative guidelines for how to score science assignments. Individual teachers may have different grading policies, but by using the same guidelines, scoring can become consistent between different students and teachers [2]. Agreement on the important qualities of student's products can allow more consistent evaluations since the performance criteria do not vary from teacher to teacher [6].

Limitations of the study and prospects for future research. The study was conducted with 10 participants only, assessing one activity. This makes it difficult to generalize the findings. Further research, involving a larger sample assessing various activities, is recommended. The stud-

ies can also involve the use of different rubrics, applied in different learning areas. This will paint a clearer picture regarding the efficacy of rubrics as an assessment tool in the classroom.

5. Conclusions

Universities, schools, and respective departments of education should ensure students and teachers are enlightened on the use of rubrics as they (rubrics) offer three primary benefits: they set clear standards of proficiency for students and for teachers to use as goals, they hold students accountable to specific standards, and they facilitate assessment by providing teachers guidelines, by which to evaluate students' learning. If used well the genius of rubrics is that they are descriptive and not evaluative [13] and assist in enhancing learning through assessment. Although they can be used to evaluate, the operating principle is the teacher matches the performance to the description rather than "judge" it [5, 7]. Thus, rubrics are as good or bad as the criteria selected and the descriptions of the levels of performance under each [5]. Effective rubrics have appropriate criteria and well-written descriptions of performance [14], which should be communicated to both the teacher and the student to enhance academic learning in the science classroom. Rubrics facilitate learning by providing students with specific feedback and allowing them to reflect on their performance in order to improve [10]. From the results of the present study, this can only happen if the rubric is in the hands of an informed and rubric-literate teacher.

Conflict of interest

The authors declare that they have no conflicts of interest.

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